

Report on the Second NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg network meeting: Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs

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During the successful first NFDI in Berlin-Brandenburg (NFDI_BB), which aimed at setting up a network of all NFDI consortia located within the region, the topic Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs was identified as a central task overarching the consortia. For more details, see also last year's report. Hence, the second NFDI_BB focused on Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs developed/used or to be developed/used within the different consortia of the NFDI. The one-day workshop took place on July 11th, 2024 from 09:30 a.m. to 03:30 p.m. at the Weierstrass Institute for Applied Analysis and Stochastics in Berlin.

Figure 1: Participants of the 2nd NFDI_BB workshop.

As many as 25 out of the 27 consortia of the NFDI are present within the Berlin-Brandenburg region, involving more than 120 scientific and other institutions. Out of 35 registered participants 25 + 2 (online) actually showed up, see Fig. 1. They came from 16 different consortia, as shown in Fig. 2. Note that a few participants belonged to more than one consortium.

Figure 2: NFDI_BB.2 participants statistics.

Morning Session A short welcome was given by Thomas Koprucki, one of the organizers, who introduced the hosting institute as well as MaRDI, the mathematical consortium of the NFDI, which is administrated at WIAS. To bring in some interactive element into the meeting, the talk was accompanied by a Mentimeter survey. Since not all of the participants do have a background in mathematics or natural sciences, they were asked about their previous visits to mathematical institutes, see Fig. 3. It turned out, that only 6 participants had never visited such an institute before this meeting.

To set the stage for the meeting, the participants were also asked to specify important terms or concepts related to the topic of the meeting, i.e., ontologies and knowledge graphs. Many of the expected terms were chosen by the participants, some clusters were found for wikidata, wikibase, sparql and metadata, see the corresponding word cloud in Fig. 4.

During the main part of the morning session, the topic Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs was presented in connection with the activities of the NFDI in four talks. The four speakers were asked ahead of time to prepare talks (with a duration of 25 + 5 minutes) providing a general overview of

Figure 3: Question on visits of a mathematical institute.

ontology development, partly using examples from their consortia. Most of these presentations can be found at the NFDI_BB community of Zenodo.

The first presentation (online) by **Tabea Tietz** was about the NFDIcore 2.0 core ontology and the NFDI4Culture knowledge graph. The NFDIcore 2.0 ontology representing the community structure and the NFDI infrastructure, was of great interest to the participants because of its nature of targeting *all* NFDI consortia. At the moment, the NFDIcore ontology is already connected to several NFDI consortia and there are plans to link to further domain-specific ontologies. Moreover, the NFDI4Culture consortium for research data of tangible and intangible cultural heritage was introduced, and its challenges for knowledge graph development were presented.

In the next presentation, **Lozana Rossenova** reported on facilitating creation, (re)use and interoperability of Knowledge Graphs in NFDI from the perspective of NFDI4Culture and Base4NFDI, which aims at interoperability with national and international research data infrastructures. The working group “Knowledge Graphs” in NFDI Section “(Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance” was introduced. The NFDI Knowledge Graph Infrastructure (KGI4NFDI) provides a central and reusable knowledge graph to support interoperability within the research domain and support the NFDI’s objectives. These goals align perfectly with the workshop goals, i.e., promoting the use of knowledge graphs by consortia, institutions and researchers and improving the FAIRness of NFDI.

Subsequently, **Olaf Simons** began his presentation with an overview of historical ontologies from the 16th century which were however abandoned in the 18th century because of the advent of dictionaries, with obvious analogies to Wikidata and Wikipedia. Then, he switched to FactGrid, a database

creation of a biodiversity knowledge graph using the Wikidata technology stack. The challenges of the data diversity were illustrated for the case of the ca. 30 million objects in the *Museum für Naturkunde* in Berlin and for the example of the 1898/99 “Valdivia” German Deep Sea Expedition.

- **Rolf Krahl** (DAPHNE4NFDI consortium) spoke about terminologies for data from Photon and Neutron (PaN) sciences, in particular the NeXus data format (based on HDF5) which is about to be expanded into an ontology. Moreover, PaNET provides a taxonomy of experimental techniques relevant for the PaN community, coming from diverse disciplines.
- **Sonja Schimmler** (NFDI4DataScience consortium) presented the NFDI4DS Research Knowledge Graphs forming the basis of the consortium infrastructure and which provides information about all kinds of digital objects such as data, models, workflows and scripts/codes along with their interrelations by using and connecting existing solutions.
- **Frank von Hagel** (NFDI4Objects consortium) talked about the progressing digitalization of museums and university collections. The NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph aims at joining a property graph with processed data and query option in Cypher with a triple-store with raw data in RDF and query option using SPARQL, thus yielding a federated system architecture.
- **Aurela Shehu** (MaRDI consortium) started with introducing the challenges of mathematical research data due to their variety and complexity. Joining the recently developed knowledge graphs on mathematical models and algorithms, the goal of MaRDI was discussed, that is at providing a flexible platform for computational and applied mathematics, to be offered also to other disciplines.

After these presentations, another Mentimeter survey was carried out. First, the participants were asked about their use of ontologies and knowledge graphs. Interestingly, it turned out that there were more developers than users in the audience, see Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Use of ontologies and knowledge graphs.

In another questionnaire, the relevance of ontologies and knowledge graphs was investigated. In general, it was rated rather high both for research scientists and for research data managers whereas the opinions on the relevance for fostering cooperation within the NFDI were found to be rather diverse, see Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Relevance of ontologies and knowledge graphs.

Moreover, there was a Mentimeter slide concerning the relation of ontologies and Knowledge Graphs (KG) with Artificial Intelligence (AI). While the majority of the participants agreed that in 10 years from now AI will use KGs, only few believed that AI will be able to generate KGs. An approximately equal number of voters were generally skeptical about the use of AI, see Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Relation of ontologies and knowledge graphs to AI.

Finally, there was a Mentimeter slide on the importance of mathematical knowledge graphs. A majority of participants stated that they see connections to their work, and quite a few others expressed their interest in the use of mathematical knowledge graphs, see Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Importance of mathematical knowledge graphs.

Final discussion During the final discussion, it became clear that the topic of ontologies and knowledge graphs was very interesting to the participants of the meeting, thus opening up potential collaboration also across consortia from diverse disciplines. The technological platforms for this are emerging these days, namely the NFDI core ontology as well as the KGI4NFDI service, provided by the NFDI section “(Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance”. This section is striving to optimize KG creation and fostering standardized ontological practices while promoting the FAIR data principles. Even though the “One NFDI” vision is still far in the future, connecting many and diverse KGs, thereby allow for federating queries is already a major step.

Finally, there is a strong interest in continuing these meetings in the future, although details have yet to be defined on what topic, location and who will be organizing the next meeting. A possible topic could be the teaching of, and raising awareness for, research data management. It is intended that the future meetings will take place bi-annually.

Contact

- For feedback on this report, and for suggesting future meeting topics, email: nfdi_bb@mardi4nfdi.de
- Participants were asked to register to the NFDI_BB mailing list https://www.listserv.dfn.de/sympa/info/nfdi_bb
Note that this list will be used as the main communication channel for information on future NFDI_BB activities.

Appendix

Agenda

09:30 - 09:50	Registration
09:50 - 10:00	Welcome
10:00 - 12:00	Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs in the NFDI
10:00 - 10:30	Tabea Tietz , “NFDIcore 2.0 and the NFDI4Culture Knowledge Graph” NFDI4Culture, NFDI Core Ontology FIZ Karlsruhe — Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure
10:30 - 11:00	Lozana Rossenova , “Facilitating creation, (re)use and interoperability of Knowledge Graphs in NFDI: perspectives from NFDI4Culture to Base4NFDI and beyond” KGI4NFDI, NFDI4Culture, German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB)
11:00 - 11:30	Olaf Simons , “If the strive for a global and eternal ontology is over, what is next? - Experiences with the FactGrid Wikibase platform.” FactGrid, NFDI4Memory, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
11:30 - 12:00	Daniel Mietchen , “NFDI-related knowledge graphs - a transdisciplinary perspective” MaRDI, FIZ Karlsruhe — Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure
12:00 - 12:05	Group photo
12:05 - 13:00	Lunch break at WIAS lobby
13:00 - 14:15	Showcases from the individual NFDI consortia
13:00 - 13:15	NFDI4Biodiversity - Sabine von Mering Natural History Museum
13:15 - 13:30	DAPHNE4NFDI - Rolf Krahl Helmholtz Centre for Materials and Energy (HZB)
13:30 - 13:45	NFDI4DataScience, Base4NFDI, NFDI4Cat - Sonja Schimmler Fraunhofer Institute for Open Communication Systems (FOKUS), Technical University of Berlin
13:45 - 14:00	NFDI4Objects - Frank von Hagel Berlin State Museums
14:00 - 14:15	MaRDI - Aurela Shehu Weierstrass Institute for Applied Analysis and Stochastics (WIAS)
14:15 - 14:45	Coffee break
14:45 - 15:30	Plenary discussion
15:30	Closing remark